

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF DUTOR INSTRUMENT IN SHAPING HUMAN EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7954083>

Abstract. *This article presents ideas for the formation of education among young people through learning to play the instrument dutor.*

Keywords: *dutor, stroke, upbringing, tradition, value, aesthetics, the younger generation, behavior.*

Introduction

Dutor is one of the oldest, widespread and favorite instruments among national instruments. on the other hand, it is valued as a craft inherited by women as a tradition from their mothers and grandmothers.

Dutor is the original mirror of Uzbek national culture, whose painful melodies seem to sing about our spirituality and values that have survived from several centuries left behind in the course of history.

Research materials and methodology

The word dutor means "two strings" in Persian. Dutor is a stringed percussion (device that makes music), widely used in Uzbek, Tadjik, Uyghur, Turkmen, and Karakalpak peoples. However, the Uzbek dutori is different from others by its rich beauty and gentleness. The cup part of Dutor soz is made of mulberry, and the handle part is made of yellow-orange wood. The length of the dutor is about 1 meter on average, depending on its type, it is shorter or longer. The cup part of this instrument is bigger compared to other instrument, and the handle is thin and long. Strings are drawn from two, twine or hemp. These strings are tuned in fourths, fifths, and sometimes together. Ties on the handle separate the curtains of the dutor.

Dutor is played by pressing the strings with the right hand and pressing the guitar-neck upset moods with the fingers of the left hand. A soloist and a person who played along in Dutor's performance require a performance skill from the person (who makes money from playing music).

Dutor strengths consist of single strength, double strength, wrist strength, reverse strength, bidartma, etc.

A single beat is one of the simple beats, which the performer learns during the first learning process. In this case, the movement of the fingers of the right hand (except the thumb) is directed downwards and upwards.

Terma zarb (tanovor zarb) is the most common type of strength, and it is mainly made with thumb and index fingers. In this case, when the hand moves down, the index first, then the thumb, and when the hand moves up, it is the other way around.

In traditional dutor performance, in addition to percussion, there are also different decorations and glosses, (in other words) qochirims, in order to make sounds sound. In the language of people (who make money from playing music), they are called by such names as nolish, miyang, kashish, to`lqinlatish. Each decoration gives the tune its own charm and shows which school of performance it belongs to.

Discussion and results

Today, dutor performance has reached the level of expertise, and his first lessons were at Children's Music and Art Schools, then at Professional Art Schools, and at the professional level at the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan and the Uzbek National Music Academy named after Yunus Rajabi. It is taught at institute. In addition, in the cultural centers of the cities and districts of our Republic, in the "Barkamol Avlod" children's schools, "Dutor performance" circles are operating on the basis of amateurs.

The decision PQ-112 of our respected President Shavkat Mirziyoyev adopted on 02.02.2022 "On additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art" states the following: "General secondary in educational institutions: students are taught the skills of playing tunes on at least one of the national musical instruments listed in Appendix 1 to this decision, and a corresponding note on their educational document (certificate) will be included"

Necessary measures are being taken to ensure the implementation of this decision.

"It is very important to teach them musical instruments in shaping the education of the young generation in accordance with our national traditions. After all, the magical sound of musical instruments penetrates deeply into the psyche of the child and turns all the feelings formed in his mind into feelings of goodness". Therefore, in the responsible work of educating the young generation, it is appropriate to refer more to the areas that teach our cultural values. However, some of our young people, along with learning and learning skills, are absorbing information on social networks that lead to various harmful vices, and are addicted to games that waste their time. As a result, there is an obstacle to the consistent development of education and training. Disrespect for parents and relatives, indifference to society, disrespect for our national traditions, and the priority of self-interest in everything are being formed among young people. After all, a person is beautiful with his behavior. If a person is highly educated and has potential, but a small form of lack of education appears in him, his intelligence is useless.

Music is one of the factors that improve human education, especially learning national instruments gives a person's good qualities, Benazir behavior.

Conclusion

The essence of teaching Dutor and similar national instruments to the young generation is as follows: It strengthens the will of young people, raises their spirituality, shapes their aesthetics, increases the feeling of universality, patriotism, and expands their worldview. No matter what field a person with executive potential and skills is a representative of, he has the characteristics of a civilized person.

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